

A Giant Retroperitoneal Dedifferentiated Liposarcoma Presenting as Progressive Constipation: A Rare Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Objective: This article presents a rare case of retroperitoneal liposarcoma in a 72-year-old male, emphasizing the clinical presentation, diagnostic process, and management strategy.

Methods: The case was approached with a combination of clinical examination, computer tomography (CT) scans, CT-guided biopsies, and FISH study. The findings were further verified by surgical examination and histopathological analysis.

Results: The patient was diagnosed with dedifferentiated liposarcoma in the retroperitoneal region, associated with amplification of the MDM2 gene. The successful treatment strategy involved complete surgical resection of the tumor, including the involved left kidney and left adrenal gland, followed by post-surgical CT scan monitoring.

Conclusion: Retroperitoneal liposarcomas, though rare, can present with non-specific symptoms like progressive constipation. Early diagnosis through modern techniques, followed by thorough surgical resection, remains a pivotal treatment approach. To our knowledge, this is the first reported case of retroperitoneal liposarcoma in Jordan, providing valuable insights into the diagnosis and management of this rare malignancy.

Keywords: Liposarcoma; Retroperitoneal; Spindle cell; MDM2 gene.

INTRODUCTION

Liposarcomas are relatively rare cancerous growths that can appear in different parts of the body but are most commonly found originating from the mesenchymal tissue in the retroperitoneal area. Here, they are associated with the poorest outcomes^[1]. Diagnosis frequently occurs at an advanced stage due to the tumor's ability to grow to a substantial size without manifesting specific symptoms. Typical presenting signs include abdominal discomfort or bloating, although the most common initial finding remains an accidental discovery of an abdominal mass during a physical check-up^[2]. The type of histopathology is crucial in estimating the likelihood of recurrence and overall mortality associated with the condition^[3]. Metastasis at a distance is exceedingly rare, but local recurrence rates tend to be high. Thus, the primary treatment approach is complete surgical removal aiming for clear margins^[4]. However, this is often complicated by the tumor's local infiltration and adherence to adjacent retroperitoneal structures, notably the kidneys and blood vessels^[1,5]. CT scan remains the primary diagnostic method for identifying retroperitoneal liposarcomas^[6]. Herein, we describe a case involving a 72-year-old male experiencing constipation for two months, eventually diagnosed with retroperitoneal liposarcoma following CT imaging, biopsy, and surgical intervention. To our knowledge, this is the first such reported case in Jordan.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 72-year-old man presented to our emergency department complaining of progressive constipation for 2

months, associated with abdominal pain and distention. He also reported losing 5 kilograms (Kg) over the past 1 month which he attributed to loss of appetite and feeling of fullness. On physical examination, the vital signs were normal, the patient seemed in discomfort, with moderately distended abdomen especially in the left upper quadrant (LUQ). On palpation of the abdomen, there was a large, firm and tender mass occupying the LUQ of the abdomen, measuring approximately 20 X 15 cm with normal overlying skin. The mass was deep with ill-defined borders. And it was dull on percussion. No other masses felt in the abdomen. On digital rectal examination (DRE), there was no abnormality in the anus or rectum, and soft stool was present. The patient's medical history included controlled hypertension and type-2 diabetes mellitus. He had a surgical history of laparoscopic cholecystectomy. He is a non-smoker with no allergies, and had no personal or family history of malignancy.

The patient was admitted to the general surgery ward for further investigation of the abdominal mass. Laboratory studies such as Complete blood count (CBC), kidney function test (KFT), liver function test (LFT) and urine analysis (UA) were requested and the results were within normal limits. A CT scan with IV contrast was done which showed an enhancing heterogeneous mass measuring 23.0 x 22.0 x 18 cm with internal septations, calcification and necrotic changes, located in the left side of abdomen and likely arising from the left kidney in the retroperitoneal area. Causing mass effect to adjacent structures, with no evidence of invasion of renal arteries. No signs of intestinal obstruction, and no other enhancing lesions seen in the abdomen or pelvis.

The patient was referred to urology clinic at a tertiary hospital that includes oncology department for further management.

A pre-operative staging CT scan of chest, abdomen and pelvis with oral and IV contrast was performed to plan the proper surgical approach.

a large exophytic heterogenous soft tissue mass lesion in relation to the upper pole of the left kidney containing extensive areas of necrosis and coarse calcification measuring about 19.8 cm x 22.5 x 25.5 cm cm (Figure 1 and Figure 2).

Figure
scan

1: Abdominal CT with oral and IV contrast, axial view, shows a large mass in the left side of the abdomen with areas of calcification and necrosis.

Figure 2: Abdominal CT with oral and IV contrast, coronal view, shows the large mass displacing abdominal organs to the right and inferomedially.

The lesion was seen displacing the left kidney inferiorly as well as the pancreas. The mesenteric vessels, bowel and stomach displaced superiorly and to the right. The left renal vein appeared severely compressed, stretched and displaced to the right but still patent. The left renal artery was abutted by the mass and appeared patent. The left adrenal gland couldn't be seen separate from the mass, it was likely to be invaded. Few necrotic retroperitoneal lymph nodes were seen in the left paraaortic and aortocaval regions. The largest was in the left paraaortic region, measuring 1.4 cm. Other abdominopelvic incidental findings seen on the scan included urinary bladder stones, enlarged prostate gland, uncomplicated colonic diverticulosis, bilateral inguinal hernias containing omental fat. No signs of bowel obstruction and no free fluid seen in the abdomen or pelvis.

The lung parenchyma was within normal limits, with few tiny intraparenchymal and pleural based nodules seen bilaterally, the largest was 3 mm in the posterior segment of right upper lobe.

Mediastinum was unremarkable with small nonspecific mediastinal lymph nodes. Degenerative changes were seen in the spine and bilateral sacroiliac (SI) joints with diffuse osteoporosis and bony islands seen in the left iliac wing and scattered in the vertebrae. The radiological suspicion was of renal cell carcinoma versus pararenal soft tissue sarcoma. Based on these findings, biopsy was advised.

CT-guided biopsies from deep and superficial sites of the tumor were taken. The histopathological examination revealed sarcomatous changes consistent with the diagnosis of liposarcoma or sarcomatoid renal cell carcinoma (RCC). Moreover, a FISH study was done on the sample and reported positive for MDM2 gene amplification.

The patient underwent whole body bone scan to detect any site of metastasis. The scan was reported to be normal.

A decision was made by the urology team to perform open left radical nephrectomy to resect the mass. The surgery was under general anesthesia and with a sterile technique. A two-way Foley catheter size 16 French (Fr) was inserted. Scrubbing and towelings were done then a Chevron incision was made. Layers were opened to the retroperitoneal cavity where a huge well-vascularized mass was identified, and seen occupying the left upper quadrant, forming extensive adhesions with the spleen superiorly and the bowel inferomedially. Dissection of the mass off the spleen and bowel was performed. As well as, off the lateral abdominal wall and left psoas muscle. The left renal pedicle was identified, and the left renal artery, vein and ureter were ligated and divided. After abdomen (Figure 3). freeing the mass all around, the mass was removed en bloc with the left kidney and left adrenal gland out of the

Figure 3: Intra-operative image of the resected mass with the attached left kidney.

A chain of grossly abnormal para-aortic lymph nodes were identified and removed. A single small diaphragmatic deposit was identified and removed.

After securing hemostasis, a Redivac drain size 16 Fr was inserted in the LUQ space. After ensuring a correct count of instruments and gauze, the incision was closed layer by layer, and dressing applied. The estimated blood loss was 2 liters. Intra-operatively, the patient received 4 units of cross-matched packed red blood cells (pRBC) and 4 units of fresh frozen plasma (FFP). Following surgery, he was admitted to the ICU for close observation, where he received another unit of pRBCs. the next day he was transferred to ward. In post-operative day 1, he was started on clear fluid diet as tolerated in addition to his maintenance fluid requirement, and was continued on prophylactic IV antibiotics. In post-operative day 7, bowel motion was resumed, and patient switched to soft diet. Drain output decreased and was removed in the same day too. He had uneventful post-operative recovery, and was discharged home in post-operative day 11 with stable vital signs, toleration of regular diet and normal bowel motion and ambulation.

On histopathological examination of the mass, the mass measured 31.0 x 25.0 x 14.0 cm, weighed more than 4 Kg, was attached to the kidney which measured 10.0 x 8.0 x 4.0 cm. On cross-sectioning, the mass was white in color. Histologically, it consisted of malignant spindle cells with prominent scattered pleomorphic cells and well-differentiated adipose tissue at the periphery (Figure 4). The tumor encased but didn't invade the kidney, and the left adrenal gland was unremarkable. The harvested lymph nodes were nine, and were found to be reactive with no evidence of malignancy. The resected diaphragmatic deposit was consistent with fragments of fibrofatty tissue with thromboses blood vessels. FISH study was performed and was positive for MDM2 gene amplification. The tumor was marginally excised with no lymphovascular or neural invasion. The diagnosis was consistent with high grade dedifferentiated liposarcoma with prominent undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma (UPS) with focal heterologous osteosarcoma components. The pathologic stage classification (pTNM, AJCC 8th edition): pT4 (more than 15 cm in greatest dimension), pN0 (no regional lymph nodes metastasis).

The patient was seen regularly at the urology clinic after discharge. A follow-up CT scan of the chest, abdomen and pelvis with oral and IV contrast was performed one month after the surgery and no recurrence was detected.

DISCUSSION

Liposarcomas in the retroperitoneal region are infrequent malignancies originating from the mesenchymal cells of the retroperitoneal space, impacting 2.5 individuals per 100,000, predominantly affecting those between the ages of 40 and 70^[7]. These tumors, capable of manifesting wherever fat tissue is present, are predominantly observed within the retroperitoneum, accounting for 12% to 40% of cases^[8]. They rank as the primary type of

retroperitoneal sarcoma, followed by leiomyosarcoma and malignant fibrous histiocytoma, frequently presenting as massive formations exceeding 20 cm at diagnosis^[1,9].

Initially, retroperitoneal liposarcomas may remain asymptomatic, growing surreptitiously within the extensive retroperitoneal space. They often reach substantial sizes before causing non-specific symptoms like abdominal discomfort or fullness due to the pressure on neighboring structures^[10]. In the case at hand, the patient experienced a two-month history of progressive constipation attributed to bowel compression by the growing tumor.

Though distant metastasis from retroperitoneal liposarcomas remains rare, a study involving 165 patients indicated that 12% presented with metastasis at diagnosis^[11]. The current case involved comprehensive evaluations, including chest CT and bone scans, which revealed no metastatic sites.

The primary diagnostic and staging tools for these sarcomas are contrast-enhanced CT scans, where dedifferentiated liposarcomas often appear as non-lipomatous masses associated with fat tissue, and prognosis worsens with calcifications^[12]. While MRI comparisons with CT scans in the context of liposarcoma diagnosis are limited, MRIs prefer extremity soft tissue evaluations owing to their multiplanar anatomical imagery and superior soft tissue delineation capabilities^[13]. Biopsy remains reserved for cases with unusual presentations or concerns about other potential diagnoses, such as lymphoma, are high. If the tumor appears non-resectable or metastatic, a biopsy becomes essential in crafting an appropriate treatment plan^[14].

From a histological perspective, liposarcomas can be categorized into five distinct types, with well-differentiated and dedifferentiated varieties prevalent in the retroperitoneal space. These varieties exhibit divergent biological behaviors^[15]. Remarkably, retroperitoneal dedifferentiated tumors are recognized as high-grade malignancies, exhibiting a 40% recurrence rate and a 20% risk of metastasis^[16]. The analyzed specimen in this case demonstrated dedifferentiated liposarcoma characteristics along with a significant MDM2 gene amplification, a marker associated with liposarcoma progression and severity^[17].

Distinguishing retroperitoneal liposarcomas from similar conditions like retroperitoneal fibrosis and angiofollicular lymph node hyperplasia is imperative, as these conditions can mimic the clinical and radiographic features of a retroperitoneal sarcoma^[16]. The differential diagnosis should also encompass potential gastrointestinal tract malignancies, pancreas, kidneys, ovaries, and bladder^[14].

The cornerstone of treating primary retroperitoneal liposarcomas is comprehensive surgical resection to achieve negative microscopic margins, significantly lowering recurrence rates, especially in high-grade varieties^[1]. The complex nature of these tumors, often involving adjacent organs, poses challenges in determining safe surgical margins. Radical resections involving nearby organs are commonly recommended for better outcomes^[18]. Open surgical approaches are the norm, but laparoscopy is a viable alternative in select cases, potentially offering

improved clinical results^[1]. In this case, the patient underwent an extensive surgical procedure involving the removal of the left kidney and adjacent structures.

Recently, Eribulin mesylate (Halaven) has been authorized for treating inoperable or metastatic liposarcomas^[19]. Though radiation and chemotherapy are promising adjunct therapies to surgical intervention, their effectiveness remains debatable^[1,14]. Following surgery, regular monitoring using MRI or CT scans is advised as per the National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN) guidelines, with specific follow-up schedules based on the tumor grade and the success of the resection^[20]. Three months post-surgery, the patient underwent a CT scan, which did not reveal any signs of recurrence or metastasis.

This case illustrates the significant clinical challenge posed by retroperitoneal liposarcomas due to their substantial size and infiltrative nature, especially in settings where the diagnosis is delayed until the advanced stages. Comprehensive surgical intervention remains the key to managing these complex malignancies, emphasizing achieving clean margins to minimize recurrence. Though the outlook remains cautious, early detection and aggressive treatment strategies can significantly influence outcomes. The case at hand underscores the imperative to consider retroperitoneal liposarcomas in the differential diagnosis when encountering significant retroperitoneal masses, enhancing the prospects for early intervention and improved patient prognosis.

Figure 4: This image shows cellular sheets of pleomorphic, undifferentiated tumor cells with atypical mitotic figures, resembling undifferentiated pleomorphic sarcoma. Rare entrapped lipoblasts are also identified. Magnification 10X.

CONCLUSION

The diagnosis and management of retroperitoneal liposarcoma remain a complex challenge due to its rare occurrence and non-specific symptomatology. In the presented case, the key to successful management was a comprehensive diagnostic approach that combined physical examination, imaging techniques, and biopsy. The role of surgical resection as a primary treatment modality was reinforced, showcasing its efficacy in ensuring complete tumor removal and potential prevention of recurrence. The case also highlighted the importance of regular follow-up imaging post-resection to monitor for potential recurrence or metastasis. This case from Jordan underlines the universality of the challenges posed by retroperitoneal liposarcomas and underscores the importance of awareness, early detection, and aggressive management.

CONSENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal on request.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

All authors have no potential competing interests or conflicts to report.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION

Nimah A Rabai - Study concept, data collection, writing the paper, reviewing the paper, final decision to publish.

Arqam Alrababah - Data collection, writing the paper, reviewing the paper.

Saleh A. Ba-shammakh - Writing the paper, reviewing the paper.

Omar Halalsheh - Data collection, reviewing the paper, final decision to publish.

Shaima A Batayha - Data collection, writing the paper.

GUARANTOR

Nimah A Rabai

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